

Service Quality, Membership Retention and Consumer Behavior as Predictors of Business Performance of a Health and Fitness Center in Beijing, China.

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Abstract: The global fitness industry, valued at \$96.7 billion in 2020 with 184 million members (Stasha, 2021), reflects the rapid growth of the wellness sector, which exceeded \$4 trillion in 2018 (Global Wellness Institute). This sustained expansion highlights the importance of key operational factors such as service quality, membership retention, and consumer behavior. This study examined these elements as predictors of business performance at Oxygen Gym, a health and fitness center in Beijing, China. A descriptive-correlational research design was employed, and data were gathered from 300 randomly selected clients using a validated and reliable survey instrument. Findings revealed that respondent-clients “strongly agreed” with the overall quality of services at Oxygen Gym, with a weighted mean of 3.48. Among the five service quality indicators, assurance, empathy, and tangibles shared the second highest ranking, each with a weighted mean of 3.49. Customer satisfaction was rated “very high,” with a weighted mean of 3.51, where accessibility (3.54) and innovation (3.52) were most favored. Clients also “strongly agreed” with consumer behavior factors, such as psychological, personal, social, and cultural influences, with a weighted mean of 3.50. Business performance showed a “very high” degree of customer loyalty (weighted mean of 4.23), and retention rates of 100%, 72%, and 80% across three years. Significant correlations were found between service quality, membership retention, consumer behavior, and customer loyalty ($p < 0.01$). Notably, tangibles significantly predicted customer loyalty ($r = 0.652$, $F = 175.792$, $p < 0.01$), indicating a moderate level of predictive strength. The study concludes that tangible service elements are key drivers of business performance through customer loyalty.

KEYWORDS:

Service Quality, Membership Retention, Consumer Behavior

I. Introduction

In 2020, the global gym industry was valued at \$96.7 billion, with over 184 million members worldwide, underscoring the growing focus on health and wellness (Stasha, 2021). This trend mirrors earlier reports from the Global Wellness Institute (GWI), which valued the wellness sector at over \$4 trillion in 2018. As people increasingly prioritize health, demand for fitness services has surged. Despite the pandemic, gymgoers remained active due to the social and community aspects of gym life, which serve as strong motivators for membership retention (Kestenbaum, 2019).

Service quality is a key factor in customer satisfaction and loyalty. Parasuraman et al. (1988), as cited by Fida et al. (2020), developed the SERVQUAL model, highlighting five

dimensions: reliability, tangibles, responsiveness, assurance, and empathy. These dimensions guide how customers evaluate service experiences.

Membership retention reflects a customer's perception of service quality relative to expectations (Tahanisaz & Shokuhyar, 2020). Consumer behavior involves the decision-making processes of individuals as they purchase and use services and is influenced by psychological, social, and personal factors (Raither, 2018). Business performance is no longer measured solely by financial success but also by non-financial indicators such as customer loyalty and retention (Taysan & Duran, 2021; Al-Gharaibah, 2020).

Numerous studies affirm the link between service quality and customer behavior. Liu et al. (2021) found that service quality positively affects customer feedback and loyalty. Macon (2020) and Othman et al. (2020) confirmed that perceived service quality leads to continued gym membership and improved retention. Calesco and Both (2021) noted that perceptions of service vary by education, gym experience, and exposure to different gyms. Polyakova and Ramchandani (2020) emphasized that well-maintained equipment and appealing ambiance are crucial to user satisfaction.

Consumer behavior is also shaped by external influences such as social media and pricing. Khisti and Raizada (2020) found that many gym users in Ahmednagar were price-sensitive, favoring free or low-cost alternatives. Gupta (2021) stressed that consumers now expect exceptional service, while Nunkoo et al. (2019) linked high satisfaction to repeat patronage and profitability. Panno (2020) noted that modern businesses must use balanced performance metrics that consider both financial and non-financial outcomes.

Taysan and Duran (2021) emphasized the importance of perceived value in fostering customer loyalty. Pradeep et al. (2020) found that price, hygiene, and service quality significantly influence retention and recommended marketing improvements to enhance customer satisfaction and well-being.

1.1 Objective of the Study

The overall objective of this study was to determine the service quality, membership retention and consumer behavior as predictors of business performance of a health and fitness center in Beijing, China.

Specifically, this study had the following aims; 1) Identify the quality of service of the health and fitness center as assessed by the clients in terms of; reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy and tangibles 2) examine the clients' level of customers satisfaction on the services of the health and fitness center 3) discern the clients' consumer behavior towards the services of the health and fitness center 4) explain the business performance of the health and fitness center in terms of; customer loyalty and customer retention rate.

II. Methods

To gather data for the study, quantitative research was utilized, with a focus on measuring variables numerically and analyzing relationships among them (Vaidya, 2020). A descriptive-correlational research design was employed to assess the relationship between service quality,

membership retention, and consumer behavior as predictors of business performance at a health and fitness center in Beijing, China (Rubite, 2020).

Stratified random sampling was used to improve precision by dividing the population into non-overlapping groups (Lemm, 2020). The sample size was determined using the Raosoft Calculator with a 95% confidence level and a 5% margin of error. The respondents were clients of Oxygen Gym, and data was collected through a researcher-made questionnaire, validated by experts in research, language teaching, and statistics. The questionnaire was tested for reliability using Cronbach’s alpha.

Statistical tools including weighted mean, Pearson r, and stepwise regression analysis were employed to analyze data and determine the predictive ability of service quality, membership retention, and consumer behavior on business performance, particularly customer loyalty and retention.

Table 1 Quality of Service of the Health and Fitness Center

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. HFC counselors always stick to their words and serve you based on the special offers on the application date.	3.43	Strongly Agree	4
2. When you have a problem, HFC staffs show a sincere interest on solving it.	3.44	Strongly Agree	3
3. HFC staffs are reliable in providing service to member	3.47	Strongly Agree	2
4. HFC keeps members’ record accurately.	3.53	Strongly Agree	1
Average	3.47	Strongly Agree	

III. Results and Discussion

**Table 1
 Quality of Service of the Health and Fitness Center as assessed
 by Clients: Reliability**

As shown in Table 1, the respondents ‘strongly agree’ with an average weighted mean of 3.47 that the quality of service of the health and fitness center was ‘very reliable’. Specifically, they ‘strongly agree’ with weighted means ranging from 3.43 to 3.53 that the center, Oxygen Gym, ‘keeps the records of the members accurately’ with a weighted mean of 3.53 (Rank 1), ‘the staffs are liable in providing service to the members’ with a weighted mean of 3.47 (Rank 2), ‘when a member has a problem, the staffs show a sincere interest on solving them’ with a weighted mean of 3.44 (Rank 3), and ‘the center’s counselors always stick to their words and serve them based on the special offers on the application date’ with a weighted mean of 3.43 (Rank 4).

Table 2
Quality of Service of the Health and Fitness Center as assessed by Clients:
Responsiveness

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. HFC employees handle your problems immediately.	3.50	Strongly Agree	1.5
2. HFC employees are eager to listen and solve problems.	3.43	Strongly Agree	4
3. HFC employees pay attention to your concerns and understand your problems.	3.49	Strongly Agree	3
4. HFC employees have never been too busy to respond to your requests.	3.50	Strongly Agree	1.5
Average	3.48	Strongly Agree	

As indicated in Table 2, the respondents ‘strongly agree’ with an average weighted mean of 3.48 that the quality of service of the health and fitness center was ‘very responsive’. In particular, they ‘strongly agree’ with weighted means ranging from 3.43 to 3.50 that the center’s ‘employees handle the clients’ problems immediately’ and ‘have never been too busy to respond to their requests’, each with a weighted mean of 3.50 (Rank 1.5), ‘the employees pay attention to their concerns and understand their problems’ with a weighted mean of 3.49 (Rank 3), and ‘the employees are eager to listen and solve problems’ with a weighted mean of 3.43 (Rank 4).

Table 3
Quality of Service of the Health and Fitness Center as assessed by Clients:
Assurance

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. HFC staffs are consistently courteous.	3.51	Strongly Agree	2
2. HFC staffs have knowledge, capability, and skill in their job responsibilities.	3.39	Strongly Agree	4
3. HFC class instructors are always aware of members’ safety while class exercises are being conducted.	3.55	Strongly Agree	1
4. You are safe while attending class exercises under class instructor’s supervision.	3.50	Strongly Agree	3
Average	3.49	Strongly Agree	

As presented in Table 3, the respondents ‘strongly agree’ with an average weighted mean of 3.49 that they were ‘highly assured’ of the quality of service of the health and fitness. As indicated, they ‘strongly agree’ with weighted means ranging from 3.39 to 3.55 that the center’s ‘class instructors are always aware of members’ safety while class exercises are being conducted’ with a weighted mean of 3.55 (Rank 1), ‘staffs are consistently courteous’ with a weighted mean of 3.51 (Rank 2), ‘they are safe while attending class exercises under class instructor’s supervision’ with a weighted mean of 3.50 (Rank 3), and ‘staffs have knowledge, capability, and skill in their job responsibilities’ with a weighted mean of 3.39 (Rank 4).

Table 4
Quality of Service of the Health and Fitness Center as assessed by Clients: Empathy

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. HFC gives you personalized attention while providing services.	3.55	Strongly Agree	1
2. HFC has operation hours convenient to all their customers	3.35	Strongly Agree	4
3. HFC has staffs who give members personal attention.	3.54	Strongly Agree	2
4. HFC staffs understand the specific needs of their customers.	3.52	Strongly Agree	3
Average	3.49	Strongly Agree	

As reflected in Table 4, the respondents ‘strongly agree’ with an average weighted mean of 3.49 that they strongly felt the ‘empathy’ of the instructors and staffs the health and fitness center. Specifically, they ‘strongly agree’ with weighted means ranging from 3.35 to 3.55 that the center ‘gives them personalized attention while providing services’ with a weighted mean of 3.55 (Rank 1), the center ‘has staffs who give members personal attention with a weighted mean of 3.54 (Rank 2), ‘the staffs understand the specific needs of their customers’ with a weighted mean of 3.52 (Rank 3), and ‘the center has operation hours convenient to all their customers with a weighted mean of 3.35 (Rank 4).

Table 5
Quality of Service of the Health and Fitness Center as assessed by Clients: Tangibles

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. HFC has modern equipment.	3.57	Strongly Agree	1
2. HFC provides a variety of class exercises.	3.36	Strongly Agree	4
3. The design of HFC facilities is striking	3.56	Strongly Agree	2
4. Employees of HFC are neat and appealing.	3.48	Strongly Agree	3
Average	3.49	Strongly Agree	

As gleaned from Table 5, the respondents ‘strongly agree’ with an average weighted mean of 3.49 to the ‘tangibles’ of the services, physical facilities and equipment of the health and fitness center. Specifically, they ‘strongly agree’ with weighted means ranging from 3.36 to 3.57 that the center ‘has modern equipment’ with a weighted mean of 3.57 (Rank 1), ‘the design of the center facilities is striking with a weighted mean of 3.56 (Rank 2), ‘the employees of center are neat and appealing’ with a weighted mean of 3.48 (Rank 3), and ‘the center ‘provides a variety of class exercises’ with a weighted mean of 3.36 (Rank 4).

Table 6
Composite Table for the Quality of Service of the Health and Fitness Center as assessed by Clients

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Reliability	3.47	Strongly Agree	5
2. Responsiveness	3.48	Strongly Agree	4
3. Assurance	3.49	Strongly Agree	2
4. Empathy	3.49	Strongly Agree	2
5. Tangibles	3.49	Strongly Agree	2
Overall Weighted Mean	3.48	Strongly Agree	

As shown in Table 6. the respondent-clients ‘strongly agree’ with an overall average of 3.48 to the quality of service of the health and fitness center, the Oxygen Gym, as to its services. From the five (5) indicators of service quality, ‘assurance’, ‘empathy’ and ‘tangibles’, each with a weighted mean of 3.49 were equally ranked #2. Ranked # 4 was ‘responsiveness’ with a weighted mean of 3.48; and ranked #5 was ‘reliability’ with a weighted mean of 3.47. This means that the respondent-clients clearly put premium on the staff’s courtesy and credibility, on the staff’s individualized and personalized attention, staff’s appearance and on the facilities and equipment.

2. Level of Membership retention on the HFC Services

Table 7
Clients’ Level of Membership retention on the Services of the Health and Fitness Center

	Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
Facilities & Equipment	1. Proper facilities	3.47	Very High	7
	2. Quality of equipment	3.50	Very High	3
	3. Hygiene and cleanliness	3.48	Very High	6
	4. Credibility	3.49	Very High	4.5
	5. Spacious changing rooms	3.49	Very High	4.5
	6. Coherent design	3.53	Very High	2
	7. Prestige	3.54	Very High	1

	Average	3.50	Very High	4
Innovation & Services	1. Economical prices	3.62	Very High	1
	2. Innovative services	3.38	Very High	7
	3. Capacity to solve problems	3.58	Very High	2
	4. Innovative equipment	3.54	Very High	3
	5. Parking services	3.48	Very High	6
	6. Offered additional entertainment	3.53	Very High	4
	7. Pleasant environment	3.52	Very High	5
	Average	3.52	Very High	2
Personnel	1. Politeness of instructors & staff	3.60	Very High	1
	2. Accuracy of information provided by the instructors	3.37	Very High	7
	3. Performance of instructors when facing problems & complaints	3.55	Very High	3
	4. Competence of instructors	3.47	Very High	5.5
	5. Number of instructors available	3.47	Very High	5.5
	6. Fitness Instructor Service/Helpfulness	3.53	Very High	4
	7. Reception Service/Helpfulness	3.56	Very High	2
	Average	3.51	Very High	3
Accessibility	1. Location of the gym	3.60	Very High	1
	2. Easy access to the gym	3.47	Very High	2
	Average	3.54	Very High	1
	Overall Weighted Mean	3.51	Very High	

As presented in Table 7, the respondent-customers' level of satisfaction on the services of health and fitness center was 'very high' with an overall weighted mean of 3.51. This means that the customers had very high degree of fulfillment. They were pleased and content with what has been experienced and received from the services of the health and fitness center along accessibility, innovation and services, personnel, and facilities and equipment of Oxygen Gym.

Specifically, they were 'very highly' satisfied with the HFC's 'accessibility' with an average weighted mean of 3.54 (Rank 1) due to the location of the gym (WM=3.60) and the easy access to the gym (WM=3.47). Likewise, they were 'very highly' satisfied with the HFC's 'innovation and services' with an average weighted mean of 3.52 (Rank 2) because of its economical prices (WM=3.62), capacity to solve problems (WM=3.58), innovative equipment (WM=3.54), offered additional entertainment (WM=3.53), pleasant environment (WM=3.52), parking services (WM=3.48), and innovative services (WM=3.38).

Further, they were 'very highly' satisfied with the HFC's 'personnel' with an average weighted mean of 3.51 (Rank 3) due to the politeness of instructors and staff (WM=3.60), reception service/helpfulness (WM=3.56), performance of instructors when facing problems and complaints (WM=3.55), fitness instructor service/helpfulness (WM=3.53), competence of instructors (WM=3.47), number of instructors available (WM=3.47), and accuracy of information provided by the instructors (WM=3.37).

Finally, they were ‘very highly’ satisfied with the HFC’s ‘facilities and equipment’ with an average weighted mean of 3.50 (Rank 4) because of prestige (WM=3.54), coherent design (WM=3.53), quality of equipment (WM=3.50), credibility (WM=3.49), spacious changing rooms (WM=3.49), hygiene and cleanliness (WM=3.48), and proper facilities (WM=3.47).

Table 8
Clients’ Consumer Behavior towards the Services of the Health and Fitness Center

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. I consider affordability as a factor for fitness club choice.	3.49	Strongly Agree	11
2. I consider convenience as a factor for fitness club choice.	3.42	Strongly Agree	15
3. I consider facilities as a factor for fitness club choice.	3.49	Strongly Agree	11
4. I want to improve my health	3.48	Strongly Agree	13.5
5. I want to lose weight	3.53	Strongly Agree	4.5
6. I want to improve my body image	3.54	Strongly Agree	1.5
7. I decide to use a fitness club based on price.	3.52	Strongly Agree	7
8. I decide to use a fitness club based on convenience	3.49	Strongly Agree	11
9. I decide to use a fitness club based on facilities	3.50	Strongly Agree	8.5
10. Health and fitness helps me to relax and unwind	3.53	Strongly Agree	4.5
11. Health and fitness gives me time to socialize	3.48	Strongly Agree	13.5
12. Health and fitness with peer group helps me reduce anxiety	3.54	Strongly Agree	1.5
13. Health/appearance benefits can be derived from health and fitness	3.53	Strongly Agree	4.5
14. Proper time management enable me to integrate health and fitness with my lifestyle	3.50	Strongly Agree	8.5
15. Convenience enables me to integrate health and fitness in my daily/weekly routines	3.53	Strongly Agree	4.5
Average	3.50	Strongly Agree	

As reflected in Table 8, the respondent-customers ‘strongly agree’ with an average weighted mean of 3.50 to all the indicators of customer behavior towards the services of the health and fitness center. This means that their behaviors were influenced by psychological, personal, social and cultural factors as consumers of the services of the center. Specifically, they ‘strongly agree’ with weighted means ranging from 3.42 to 3.54 to the indicators that ‘I want to improve my body image’ and ‘health and fitness with peer group helps me reduce anxiety’ (Rank 1.5), ‘I want to lose weight’, ‘Health and fitness helps me to relax and unwind’, ‘Health/appearance benefits can be derived from health and fitness’, and ‘Convenience enables me to integrate health and fitness in my daily/weekly routines’ (Rank 4.5). Further, they ‘strongly agree’ to the following indicators: ‘I want to improve my health’ and ‘Health and fitness gives me time to socialize’ (Rank 13.5), and I consider convenience as a factor for fitness club choice (Rank 15).

Table 9
Business Performance of the Health and Fitness Center:
Customer Loyalty and Customer Retention

Indicators	Weighted Mean	Verbal Interpretation	Rank
1. Recommend Oxygen Gym’s facilities and services to others – a family member or friend.	4.23	Very High	2
2. Visit Oxygen Gym again for follow-up exercise classes and other services	4.23	Very High	2
3. Choose Oxygen Gym for future health and fitness services	4.23	Very High	2
Average	4.23	Very High	

The degree of customer loyalty was used as a qualitative measure of Oxygen Gym’s business performance. As shown in Table 9, the customers’ degree of loyalty was ‘very high’ with an average weighted mean of 4.23. They intimated that they would ‘recommend Oxygen Gym’s facilities and services to others – a family member or friend’, ‘visit Oxygen Gym again for follow-up exercise classes and other services’ and ‘choose Oxygen Gym for future health and fitness services’, each with a weighted mean of 4.23 (Rank 2).

Further, the customer retention rate was computed for calendars years 2018-2019, 2019-2020 and 2020-2021 resulting in a retention rate of 100%, 72% and 80% respectively. Thus, the business performance of Oxygen Gym, a 7-star health and fitness center, could be characterized as highly effective commercially.

Table 10
Relationship between Quality of Service and Clients’ Level of Membership retention on the Health and Fitness Center’s Services

Quality of Service	Pearson r	p-value	Interpretation
Reliability	0.976** High Correlation	0.000	Significant
Responsiveness	0.971** High Correlation	0.000	Significant
Assurance	0.971** High Correlation	0.000	Significant
Empathy	0.978** High Correlation	0.000	Significant
Tangibles	0.981** High Correlation	0.000	Significant
** Significant @ 0.01			

As presented in Table 10, the health and fitness center’s quality of service significantly correlated with the level of membership retention on the services shown by the Pearson r values of 0.976 for reliability, 0.971 for responsiveness, 0.971 for assurance, 0.978 for empathy, and 0.981 for tangibles and their corresponding computed p-values of 0.000 which were all less

than the 0.01 level of significance. This means that the more the customers or clients agree or attest to the quality of service of Oxygen Gym, the higher is their level of membership retention on its various services.

Table 11

Relationship between Clients’ Level of Membership retention and Consumer Behavior towards the Health and Fitness Center’s Services

	Pearson r	p-value	Interpretation
Clients’ Level of Membership retention and Consumer Behavior towards the Health and Fitness Center’s Services	0.984** High Correlation	0.000	Significant
** Significant @ 0.01			

As indicated in Table 11, there was a significant relationship between level of membership retention and consumer behavior towards the health and fitness center’s services as indicated by the Pearson r of 0.984 and the computed p-value of 0.000 which was less than 0.01 level of significance. This means that customer behavior was dependent on their level of satisfaction on the center’s services.

Table 12

Relationship between Quality of Service and Business Performance (Loyalty) of the Health and Fitness Center

Quality of Service	Pearson r	p-value	Interpretation
Reliability	0.961** High Correlation	0.000	Significant
Responsiveness	0.958** High Correlation	0.000	Significant
Assurance	0.958** High Correlation	0.000	Significant
Empathy	0.962** High Correlation	0.000	Significant
Tangibles	0.969** High Correlation	0.000	Significant
** Significant @ 0.01			

As reflected in Table 12, the quality of service of the health and fitness center significantly correlated with business performance particularly with its indicator customer loyalty as shown by the Pearson r values of 0.961 for reliability, 0.958 for responsiveness, 0.958 for assurance, 0.962 for empathy, and 0.969 for tangibles and their corresponding computed p-values of 0.000 which were all less than 0.01 level of significance. This implies that the more the customers agree or attest to the quality of service of Oxygen Gym by patronizing its services, the better is the business performance of the gym in terms of customer loyalty.

Table 13
Stepwise Regression between Service Quality, Level of Membership retention, Consumer Behavior and Business Performance of the Health and Fitness Center

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	.671	.273		2.460	.015
Tangibles	1.019	.077	.652	13.259	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Loyalty					
r = 0.652 ^a F = 175.792; p = 0.000					

As gleaned from Table 13, the quality of service in terms of tangibles predicted the business performance in terms of loyalty. The probability value of 0.000 was less than the 0.01 significance level. In addition, there was a correlation between the two variables of the study. A value of 0.652 indicates a moderate level of prediction of customer loyalty as an indicator of business performance. Further, the F-value of 175.792 with probability value of 0.000 which is less than the 0.05 significance level shows that the independent variable quality of service in terms of tangibles statistically significantly predicted the dependent variable customer loyalty as an indicator of business performance. This means that the more the customers agree or attest to the quality of service rendered by Oxygen Gym along tangibles, the higher is the customers' degree of loyalty which could result in the gym's being commercially effective. Only the tangibles predicted HFC's business performance with customer loyalty as an indicator.

IV. Conclusion and Recommendation

The Oxygen Gym has the ability to deliver service dependably and accurately. Its employees have the willingness to provide timely and efficient service for their clients and demonstrate the ability to convey trust and confidence to its clients, such as the knowledge and competence to answer questions. The instructors and staffs are able to provide treatment that is individualized care and attention to center members, such as personalized attention; and staffs understand the needs of individual members. The clients or customers are attracted and drawn to its modern equipment, well-designed club, neat and well-dressed staffs and a variety of class exercises.

The clients have very high degree of fulfillment and are very pleased and content with what has been experienced and received from the services of the health and fitness center along accessibility, innovation and services, personnel, and facilities and equipment of Oxygen Gym.

The clients' behavior is influenced by psychological, personal, social and cultural factors as consumers of the services of the center.

The business performance of Oxygen Gym, a 7-star health and fitness center, can be characterized as highly effective commercially based on the clients' very high degree of loyalty and on its customer retention rate for the past three (3) years.

The more the customers or clients agree or attest to the quality of service of Oxygen Gym, the higher is their level of membership retention on its various services; the more they agree or attest to the quality of service of Oxygen Gym, the better is the business performance of the gym in terms of customer loyalty; and that customer behavior is dependent on their level of satisfaction on the center's services.

The more the customers or clients agree or attest to the quality of service rendered by Oxygen Gym along tangibles, the higher is the customers' degree of loyalty which can result in the gym's being commercially effective. Thus, tangibles as a quality service indicator appear to be a predictor of business performance based on the degree of customer loyalty.

Recommendations

Since the clients of Oxygen Gym clearly put premium on the staff's courtesy and credibility, on the staff's individualized and personalized attention, staff's appearance and on facilities and equipment, which all fall under the quality service indicators of assurance, empathy and tangibles, management should continually sustain its staff development program on personal development and customer relations; and maintain its state-of-the-art facilities and equipment to stay on top as a reputable and the biggest health and fitness club in Beijing China.

Though the clients expressed a very high level of satisfaction on the services of Oxygen Gym, management should include in its continuous quality improvement plan the maintenance of the gym's hygiene and cleanliness 24/7. Expansion of facilities like a bigger pool, spa and restaurant may be considered. Amid the pandemic, innovative services like online booking may be explored and adopted.

The marketing department of Oxygen Gym should consider the factors that inhibit or drive clients to avail of the gym's services such psychological, personal, social and cultural factors. Knowledge on these factors is important in the formulation of marketing strategies to attract more clients. For instance, improving one's body image and being with peers in the gym to reduce anxiety were found to be drivers or motivators to go to the gym.

Customer loyalty and customer retention rate are two qualitative measures used in determining business performance. Such was the case for Oxygen Gym which was found to be a commercially effective. In the future, Oxygen Gym, if possible, may look into its financial statements to quantitatively measure business success. A combination of both qualitative and quantitative may ideally be considered.

Since in the case of Oxygen Gym, membership retention and business performance were very highly associated with the quality of services, the management and its personnel should revisit the indicators of quality services and the gym's services such facilities and equipment, innovation and services, personnel, and accessibility and identify areas for improvement like the expansion of facilities (ex. upgrading of diet center), offering innovative services (ex. downloadable online programs), and looking into the accuracy of information provided by instructors, etc.

Tangibles among other service quality indicators singly predicted HFC's business performance with customer loyalty as an indicator. Since the Oxygen Gym is a 7-star health and fitness center with rich Beijing, China clients, they put more premium on the design of the gym, physical facilities, modern equipment, and a variety of class exercises. Thus, it behooves management to regularly maintain a state-of-the-art gym by continuously expanding and re-designing its facilities, acquiring new equipment and innovating its services tapping online platforms to be able to retain its customers, stay competitive, and discourage the entry of new competitors.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed, U., Al-Balushi, Y., Fida, B. A. & Singh, D. (2020). Impact of Service Quality on Customer Loyalty and Membership retention in Islamic Banks in the Sultanate of Oman. *SAGE Journals*.
- Al-Gharabiah, O.B (2020). Customer retention in five-star hotels in Jordan: The mediating role of hotel perceived value. *Management Science Letters*
- Almohaimmed, B. (2019). Pillars of customer retention: An empirical study on the influence of membership retention, customer loyalty, customer profitability on customer retention. *Serbian Journal of Management*
- Alves, G. R. (2014). Measuring Membership retention in Services Industry. (Master's Thesis). Católica-Lisbon School of Business and Economics.
- Angelova, B. & Zekiri, J. (2011). Measuring Membership retention with Service Quality Using American Membership retention Model (ACSI Model). *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 1 (3), 232 – 258.
- Anggraeni, F.S. (2020). Green Marketing Exploration on Customer Retention in Improving Business Performance with Tacit Entrepreneurship Knowledge as Moderator. *Journal of Digital Marketing and Halal Industry*. DOI: 10.21580/jdmhi.2020.2.2.6351
- Apuke, O.D. (2017). Quantitative Research Methods a Synopsis Approach. *Arabian Journal of Business and Management Review (Beijing, China Chapter)*. Vol 6 (10).
- Arachige, J. J. G., Singh, D., & Weerasooriya, W. (2021). Examining the Relationship Between Competitive Capability and Perceived Service Quality in University Libraries. *Journal of the University Librarians Association of Sri Lanka*. 24 (1). 10.4038/jula.v24i1.8042.
- Aristayasa, I. P., Paramita, N. L. P. S. P., Suciptawati, N. L. P. (2019). Membership retention analysis based on service quality: case of local credit provider in Bali. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*. Retrieved from <https://iopscience.iop.org/article/10.1088/1742-6596/1321/2/022055/pdf>.
- Balinado, J. R., Prasetyo, Y. T., Young, M. N., Persada, S. F., Miraja, B. A., Perwira Redi, A. A. N. The Effect of Service Quality on Membership retention in an Automotive After-Sales Service. *J. Open Innov*, 7, 116. <https://doi.org/10.3390/joitmc7020116>.
- Bamberger, B., Homburg, C., & Wielgos, D. M. (2021). EXPRESS: Wage Inequality: Its Impact on Membership retention and Firm Performance. *Journal of Marketing*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1177/00222429211026655>.
- Bandyopadhyay, N. (2018). Whether service quality determinants and membership retention influence loyalty: A study of fitness services. *International Journal of Business Excellence*. DOI: 10.1504/IJBEX.2018.093875.
- Bengtsson, S., Hertzberg, J., & Rask, L. (2020). *Service Quality, Membership retention and Brand Loyalty*. (Bachelor's Thesis). Jonkoping University.

- Bermudo, P.J., Araojo, A., Morales, M., & Yango, A. (2013). *Research Made Simple: A Guide to Graduate and Undergraduate Research*. Manila: Mindshapers, Inc.
- Bhasin, H. (2021). The Servqual Model – Definition, Dimensions, Gaps and Advantages <https://www.marketing91.com/servqual/#:~:text=The%20current%20five%20dimension%20of%20understanding%20the%20customer%2C%20and%20tangibles>.
- Borgave, S. & Koranne, S. (2016). *Service Quality Management*. Retrieved from <https://www.researchgate.net>.
- Byon, K. K., Choi, H., Kim, K. (2020). A Conceptual Analysis of Switching Costs: Implications for Fitness Centers. *Sustainability*, 12 (9), 3891.
- Calesco, V.A. & Both, J. (2021). Quality Services provided by gyms. *Retos*. DOI: 10.47197/retos.v0i39.77659
- Camilleri, E. & Miah, S. J. (2021). Evaluating Latent Content Within Unstructured Text: An Analytical Methodology Based on a Temporal Network of Associated Topics. *Journal of Big Data*, 8 (1), <https://journalofbigdata.springeropen.com/articles/10.1186/s40537-021-00511-0>.
- Carvalho, M. J., Goncalves, C. & Meireles, P. (2016). Consumer Behaviour in Fitness Club: Study of the Weekly Frequency of Use, Expectations, Satisfaction and Retention. *The Open Sports Sciences Journal*, 9, 62 – 70.
- Cavacece, Y., Granata, G., Russo, G., Tartaglione, A. M. (2019). A Systematic Mapping Study on Customer Loyalty and Brand Management. *Administrative Sciences*, 9 (8), 2 – 21.
- Chandra, S., Chandra, T., Ng, M., & Priyono (2018). The Effect of Service Quality on Student Satisfaction and Student Loyalty: An Empirical Study. *Journal of Social Studies Education Research*. 9 (3), 109 – 131.
- Chatzi, S., Kissa, D., & Peitzika, E. (2020). Service Quality Expectations in the Fitness Center Context: A Validation of the Expectations Component of the SERVQUAL Scale in Greece. *Services Marketing Quarterly*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1080/15332969.2020.1742977>.
- Darzi, M.A & Bhat, S.A. (2018). Personnel capability and membership retention as predictors of customer retention in the banking sector: A mediated-moderation study. *International Journal of Bank Marketing*
- Di Crosta, A. et al. (2021). Psychological factors and consumer behavior during the COVID-19 pandemic. *PLoS ONE*. DOI: 10.1371/journal.pone.0256095
- Dobrovic, J., Lambovska, M., Gallo, P. & Tikova, V. (2018). Non-financial indicators and their importance in small and medium-sized enterprises. *Journal of Competitiveness*. 10 (2)
- Elestwani, S. F. (2015). *Transfer Effect of Trust, Satisfaction and Loyalty Link: Building Loyalty Relationships through an E-Contact Center*. (Master's Thesis). University of Houston.
- Elestwani, S. F. (2018). *The Effect of Postsecondary Education and Previous Work Experience on Clinical Competence: A Quantitative Analysis of Neurodiagnostic Technologists' Credentialing Examinations*. (Doctoral Dissertation). University of Houston.
- Farooq, M.S., Salam, M., Fayolle, A., Jaafar, N., & Ayupp, K. (2018). Impact of service quality on membership retention in Malaysia airlines: A PLS-SEM Approach. *Journal of Air Transport Management*. 67.
- Fida, B.A., Ahmed, U., & Al-Balushi, Y. (2020). Impact of Service Quality on Customer Loyalty and Membership retention in Islamic Banks in the Sultanate of Oman. *SAGE Open*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1177/2158244020919517>.

- Freitas, A.L.P. & Lacerda, T.S. (2018). Fitness Centers: What are the most important attributes in this sector? *International Journal for Quality Research* 13(1). DOI - 10.24874/IJQR13.01-11
- Gocłowska, S., Piatkowska, M., & Lenartowicz, M. (2019). Membership retention and its Measurement in Fitness Clubs of Warsaw. *Economics & Sociology*. 12 (2), 205 - 218. doi:10.14254/2071-789X.2019/12-2/12.
- Goncalves, C. (2018). Compreender a retenção de membros em centros de fitness: Um estudo em áreas urbanas de Portugal. *Revista Gerencia Deportiva*, 2 (1), 3 – 65.
- Gonçalves, C. & Diniz, A. (2015). Analysis of member retention in fitness through satisfaction, attributes perception, expectations and well-being. *Revista Portuguesa de Marketing*. Vol. 38, No. 34, pp. 65-76 Available from:
- Grants, J., Jasinkas, E., Simanavicius, A., Svagzdiene, B., & Vazne, Z. (2018). The Success of Learning Organization: Values Contextualization Dimension. *International Journal of Learning and Teaching*, 10 (4), 381 –3 88.
- Gunawan, I., Susan, M., & Winarto, J. (2021). Development of Service Quality Model as Determinants toward Banking Performance. *Studies of Applied Economics*. 39 (4).
- Gupta, C. (2021). What is membership retention? (And How to Achieve it?). Retrieved from <https://www.zendesk.com/blog/3-steps-achieving-customer-satisfaction-loyalty/>.
- Guzel, P., Polat, E., & Yildiz, K. (2018). A Study Investigating the Perceived Service Quality Levels of Sport Center Members: A Kano Model Perspective, *Journal of Education and Training Studies*, 6 (4). Retrieved from <https://pdfs.semanticscholar.org/7d37/041f257404f7549096e55d736dcecc0ab0f3.pdf>.
- Hagger, M. S. (2019). The Reasoned Action Approach and the Theories of Reasoned Action and Planned Behavior.
- Ijara, T. M. (2020). Service Quality and Financial Performance of Banks (A Meta-Analysis). *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications (IJSRP)*, 10 (5), 349 - 359.
- Ikhsan, R.B. et al (2018). Customer retention as a result of behavioural intention: Relationship between customer orientation of service employee and service quality. *Pertanika Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*.
- Jariyachamsit, S (2021). Effect of Customer Loyalty, Innovative Management, Knowledge Management and Marketing Management on Business Performance of Three Stars Hotel in Eastern Region of Thailand. *Review of International Geographical Education Online*. DOI: 10.48047/rigeo.11/5/37
- Jasinskas, E., Reklaitiene, D., Svagzdiene, B. (2013). Evaluation of Service Quality in Fitness Centres, *Transformations in Business & Economics*, 12, 1 (28), 108-124.
- Ken Research (2018). *SWOT Analysis of Beijing, China Fitness Service Market: Ken Research*. Retrieved from <https://www.kenresearch.com/blog/2018/09/swot-analysis-of-Beijing, China-fitness-service-market-ken-research/>.
- Kestenbaum, R. (2019). The Biggest Trends In Gyms And The Fitness Industry. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/richardkestenbaum/2019/11/20/the-biggest-trends-in-gyms-and-the-fitness-industry/?sh=5ea93da7465d>
- Ketut Kanten & Darma, G. S. (2017). Consumer Behaviour, Marketing Strategy, Membership retention, and Business Performance. *Jurnal Manajemen dan Bisnis*.
- Khisti, Y. & Raizada, S. (2020). A Study on Consumer Behaviour to Joining Gym in Ahmednagar. *Annals of Tropical Medicine and Public Health*.
- Kierczak, L. (n.d.) Membership retention: Why It's Still Important in 2021. Retrieved from <https://survicate.com/customer-satisfaction/importance-customer-satisfaction/>.

- Klokkenga, B. (2020). How to measure the 5 dimensions of service quality. <https://www.getfeedback.com/resources/cx/how-to-measure-the-5-dimensions-of-service-quality/>. Accessed 07 April 2022.
- Kobiruzzaman, M. M. (2022). *Five Dimensions of Service Quality- Servqual Model of Service Quality*. Newsmoor- Best Online Learning Platform. <https://newsmoor.com/servqual-model-five-key-service-dimensions-servqual-gaps-reasons/>
- Kordestani, A., Ohgazi, P., Peighambari, K., & Satari, S. (2016). Consumer Behavior Research: A Synthesis of the Recent Literature. *SAGE Journal*. 1 – 9.
- Lasadika, M. R. (2018). *The Impact of Service Quality toward Customer Loyalty through Membership retention and Trust as a Mediating Variable*. (Bachelor's Thesis). Universitas Islam Indonesia. Retrieved from <https://dspace.uii.ac.id/bitstream/handle/123456789/5756/THESIS%20M.RASIS%20L.A.SADIKA%2012311485.pdf?sequence=1>.
- Liu, L., Cui T., & Ye, Y. (2021). Encouraging Tourist Citizenship Behavior through Resource Uniqueness and Service Quality: The Mediating Role of Emotions. *Journal of Vacation Marketing*.
- Lobasenko, V. (2017). *Consumer Behavior towards Innovative Products: Which methodologies for which values?* (Doctoral Dissertation). Université Grenoble Alpes.
- Kanten, I K. & Sri Darma, G. (2017). Consumer Behaviour, Marketing Strategy, Membership retention, and Business Performance. *Jurnal Manajemen Bisnis*
- Kartika, C., Hidayat, F. & Krinala, E. (2019). Effects of Relationship in Marketing, Marketing Communication, Corporate Image on the Intention of Consumer Behavior through Membership retention at Vasa Hotel Surabaya. *Jmm17*. DOI: 10.30996/jmm17.v6i02.2992
- Macon, R. W. (2020). *Customer Retention Strategies in the Fitness Industry*. (Doctoral Dissertation). Walden University.
- Maksimović, N. et al. (2017). Quality of services in fitness centers: Importance of physical support and assisting staff. *South African Journal for Research in Sport, Physical Education and Recreation*. DOI: 10.4314/sajrs.v39i3
- Maria, F. F., Nathan, R. J., Thoppan, J. J., & Victor, V. (2018). Factors Influencing Consumer Behavior and Prospective Purchase Decisions in a Dynamic Pricing Environment—An Exploratory Factor Analysis Approach. *Social Sciences*. 7, 2 – 14.
- Maryam, A., Marzieh, T., & Marzieh, G. (2014). Relationship among Market Orientation, Service Quality and Organizational Performance from perspective of Gonbad Kavoo's Telecommunication Firm Employees. *Advances in Applied Science Research*, 5(3) ,464 - 466.
- Mathew, J. (2021). Drivers of Customer Retention: An Introspection Into Indian Retail Customers. *Vision*. DOI: 10.1177/09722629211043592
- Maulana, F. (2019). Pengaruh Kualitas Pelayanan Dan Experiential Marketing Terhadap Loyalitas Pelanggan Pada Pusat Kebugaran Dgym Apita Cirebon. *Indonesian Journal of Strategic Management*. DOI: 10.25134/ijsm.v2i2.1971
- Moon, H. C. & Zhong, Y. (2020). What Drives Membership retention, Loyalty, and Happiness in Fast-Food Restaurants in China? Perceived Price, Service Quality, Food Quality, Physical Environment Quality, and the Moderating Role of Gender. *Foods*. 9, 460, 2 – 19. doi:10.3390/foods9040460.
- Nair, G. (2016). Impact of Service Quality on Business Performance in Hospitality Industries: An empirical study. *Journal of Tourism, Hospitality and Sports*. www.iiste.org ISSN

(Paper) 2312-5187 ISSN (Online) 2312-5179 An International Peer-reviewed Journal
Vol.17, 10.

- Narkunienė, J. & Ulbinaitė, A. (2018). Comparative analysis of company performance evaluation methods, *Entrepreneurship and Sustainability Issues* 6(1): 125-138.
- Nelson, S. (2019). Why The Wellness Business Is Booming (And How To Succeed In The Industry).
<https://www.forbes.com/sites/forbesbusinessdevelopmentcouncil/2019/10/14/why-the-wellness-business-is-booming-and-how-to-succeed-in-the-industry/?sh=6577318841aa>
- Nia, S. K. & Razaghi, S. (2014). *Benefits and Challenges of a Loyalty Program*. (Master's Thesis). Luleå University of Technology. Retrieved from <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1027885/FULLTEXT02>
- Nugroho, S., Kempa, S., & Panjaitan, T.W.S. (2020). Logistic Service Quality and Membership retention to Customer Retention on Rice Producer Industry. *SHS Web of Conferences* (2020) Vol. 76
- Nunkoo, R., Teeroovengadum, V., Ringle, C., & Sunnassee, V. (2019). Service Quality and Membership retention: The Moderating Effects of Hotel Star Rating. *Int. J. Hosp. Manag.* 91, 102414.
- Nurmaliki, S. & Riyanto, S. (2020). The Influence of Consumer Behavior, Competitive Advantages on the Performance of MSMEs during Covid-19. *International Journal of Innovative Science and Research Technology*.
- Odeny, B. A. (2016). *The Influence of Service Quality on Performance of Barclays Bank of Kenya Limited*. (Master's Thesis). University of Nairobi. Retrieved from http://erepository.uonbi.ac.ke/bitstream/handle/11295/98762/Odeny_The%20Influence%20Of%20Service%20Quality%20On%20Performance%20Of%20Barclays%20Bank%20Of%20Kenya%20Limited.pdf?sequence=1
- Omar Ali, S. R. & Abd Hakim Amir, S. N. (2020). Service Quality and Membership retention: Experience of Customers in Postal Service. *Jurnal Intelek*.
- Othman, B. et al. (2020). Effect of service quality on service value and customer retention for clothing store brands in China. *Tekstilec*. Vol 63 (4).
- Ovadhah, A. (2014). *The Social Identity of Customer Loyalty in a B2B Service Environment*. (Master's Thesis). Universiteit van Amsterdam.
- Panno, A. (2020). Performance measurement and management in small companies of the service sector; evidence from a sample of Italian hotels. *Measuring Business Excellence*, Vol. 24 No. 2, pp. 133-160. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MBE-01-2018-0004>
- Pantjoro, A. (2020). The Effect of Service Quality in the Formation of Brand Image: Fitness Center in Bekasi, West Java, Indonesia. *International Journal of Multicultural and Multireligious Understanding*. DOI: 10.18415/ijmmu.v7i11.2144
- Parasuraman, A., Zeithaml, V. A., & Berry, L. L. (1988). SERVQUAL: A Multiple-item Scale for Measuring Consumer Perceptions of Service Quality. *Journal of Retailing*, 64 (1), 12-37.
- Phuc, C. C. (2019). *Loyalty Rewards Program and Membership Holders' Satisfaction*. (Bachelor's Thesis). Saimaa University of Applied Sciences.
- Pick, M. (2021). Psychological ownership in social media influencer marketing *European Business Review*. DOI: 10.1108/EBR-08-2019-0165

- Polyakova, O. & Ramchandani, G. (2020). Perceived service quality among regular users of gyms in public sports centers in the UK. *Managing Sport and Leisure*. DOI: 10.1080/23750472.2020.1853594
- Pradeep, S., Vadakepat, V & Rajasenan, D. (2020). The effect of service quality on membership retention in fitness firms. *Management Science Letters* , 10(9), 2011-2020.
- Ranabhat, D. (2018). *Customer Loyalty in Business: Views of students of Centria University of Applied Sciences*. (Bachelor's Thesis). Centria University. Retrieved from <https://www.theseus.fi/bitstream/handle/10024/142883/Ranabhat%20Durga%20.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y>.
- Raither, P. (2018). The Impact of Consumers' Actual Behaviour on Social Media on their Purchase Behaviour. (Master's Thesis). Dublin Business School. Retrieved from https://esource.dbs.ie/bitstream/handle/10788/3570/msc_raithel_p_2018.pdf?sequence=1&isAllowed=y.
- Rego, Lopo L.; Morgan, Neil A. and Fornell, Claes (2013). Reexamining the Market Share – Membership retention Relationship. *Journal of Marketing*, 77(5): 1-20.
- Rodrigues, R.G. et al. (2017). Segmentation of Portuguese Customers' Expectations from Fitness Programs. *Journal Of International Studies*.
- Rosete, E. N. et al. (2021). Organizational Support, organizational Justice, Employee Engagement and Job Performance of Allied Sciences Faculty. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Academic Research* Vol. 9, No. 2.
- Sampaio, C.A.F., Mogollón, J.M.H & Rodrigues, R.J. (2020). The relationship between market orientation, customer loyalty and business performance: A sample from the Western Europe hotel industry. *Tourism and Hospitality Research*. DOI: 10.1177/1467358419829179
- Serrano, C. I., Shah, V., & Abramoff, M. D. (2018). Use of Expectation Disconfirmation Theory to Test Patient Satisfaction with Asynchronous Telemedicine for Diabetic Retinopathy Detection. *International Journal of Telemedicine and Applications*. Retrieved from <https://doi.org/10.1155/2018/7015272>
- Sihombing, S. O. & Suwono, L.V. (2016). Factors Affecting Customer Loyalty of Fitness Centers: An Empirical Study. *Jurnal Dinamika Manajemen*, 7 (1), 45 – 55. <http://jdm.unnes.ac.id>.
- Somphong, S., Kutintara, I. & Rattamane, K. (2019). The marketing factors influencing consumer decisions to use the services of sports and exercise centers in Thailand. *African Journal of Hospitality, Tourism and Leisure*.
- Sonpal, S. (2019). Consumer Behavior: A Study of Bhavnagar City's Fitness and Health Clubs. *International Journal of Scientific Development and Research (IJS DR)* Volume 4, Issue 4 IJS DR1904091 www.ijdsr.org 435
- Srivastava, M. & KrRai, A. (2018). Mechanics of engendering customer loyalty: A conceptual framework. *IIMB Management Review*. Vol. 30, Issue 3.
- Stasha, S. (2021). 19+ Statistics and Facts about the Fitness Industry (2021). <https://policyadvice.net/insurance/insights/fitness-industry-statistics/>
- Sukiri (2021). Membership retention with fitness services and equipment facilities in gym academic faculty of science, Jakarta State University. *Gladi : Jurnal Ilmu Keolahragaan*. DOI: 10.21009/gjik.121.06
- Tahanisaz, S. & Shokuhyar, S. (2020). Evaluation of Passenger Satisfaction with Service Quality: A Consecutive Method Applied to the Airline Industry. *J. Air Transp. Manag.* 83, 101764.

- Taysan, N. & Duran, C. (2021). The antecedents of customer loyalty. *Contemporary Issues with Multidisciplinary Perspectives on Social Science*. DOI: 10.1177/109467059914007
- Thanabordeekij, P. (2018). The Influence of Perceived Service Quality on Fitness Membership Renewal of XYZ Fitness. *Journal of Management Sciences*, Vol. 5 (2) (2018)
- Uğurlu, F.M. (2018). Satisfaction Levels of Individuals Who Go to Fitness Centers. *Universal Journal of Educational Research* 6(10): 2266-2270, 2018 <http://www.hrpub.org> DOI: 10.13189/ujer.2018.061025
- Vo, N. T., Chovancová, M. & Tri, H.T. (2020). The Impact of E-service Quality on the Membership retention and Consumer Engagement Behaviors Toward Luxury Hotels. *Journal of Quality Assurance in Hospitality and Tourism*. DOI: 10.1080/1528008X.2019.1695701
- Wende, R. M. (2019). Influence of relationship marketing on customer loyalty in the telecommunication industry in Dar es salaam, Tanzania. (Master's Thesis). Strathmore University.
- Wijetunge, W. A. D. S. (2016). Service Quality, Competitive Advantage and Business Performance in Service Providing SMEs in Sri Lanka. *International Journal of Scientific and Research Publications*, 6 (7), 720 – 728, ISSN 2250-3153.
- Yusof, A., Popa, A., & Geok, S. K. (2018). Relationship between Perceptions of Fitness Facility Service Quality and Future Intentions of Fitness Center Users in Thailand. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 8(7), 863–871.
- Zopiatis, A. et al. (2017). Quality, Satisfaction and Customers' Future Intention: The Case of Hotels' Fitness Centers in Cyprus. *Journal of Quality Assurance in Hospitality and Tourism*. DOI: 10.1080/1528008X.2015.1133366